

**Individual efficacy and community impact of ivermectin,
diethylcarbamazine and albendazole mass drug administration for
lymphatic filariasis control in Fiji: a cluster randomised trial**

Short title: Lymphatic filariasis control in Fiji

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Key points: In a setting of diurnally subperiodic lymphatic filariasis, we observed no difference in individual clearance of microfilariae 12 months after mass drug administration with either dual therapy (diethylcarbamazine and albendazole) or triple therapy (ivermectin, ivermectin, diethylcarbamazine and albendazole).

Abstract

Background

Bancroftian filariasis remains endemic in Fiji despite over 10 years of mass drug administration (MDA) using diethylcarbamazine and albendazole (DA). The addition of ivermectin to this combination (IDA) has improved efficacy of microfilarial clearance at 12 months in individually randomised trials in nocturnal transmission settings, but impact in a setting of diurnally subperiodic filarial transmission has not been evaluated.

Methods

This cluster randomised study compared the individual efficacy and community impact of IDA versus DA as MDA for lymphatic filariasis in 35 villages on two islands of Fiji. Participants were tested at enrolment for circulating filarial antigen and, if positive, for microfilariae (Mf). Weight-dosed treatment was offered according to village randomisation. Communities were visited at 12 months and retested for lymphatic filariasis. Infected individuals from Rotuma retested at 24 months.

Results

3816 participants were enrolled and 3616 treated. At 12 months, Mf clearance was achieved in 72 of 111 participants detected with infection at baseline, with no difference in efficacy between treatment groups: DA 69.2%, 95% CI 57.2–79.1% versus IDA 62.5%, 43.6–78.2%, risk difference 11.3 %, 95% CI -10–32.7%, $P = 0.30$. There was no difference between treatment groups in community prevalence of Mf at 12 months or individual clearance at 24 months.

Conclusions

We found no difference between IDA and DA in individual clearance or community prevalence of lymphatic filariasis at 12 months, and no improved efficacy following a second annual round of IDA. Possible explanations for the apparent lack of benefit of IDA compared to DA include drug and parasite factors affecting clearance, and higher than expected re-infection rates.

Introduction

Wuchereria bancrofti is a parasitic filarial round-worm responsible for the neglected tropical disease, lymphatic filariasis (LF). The immature worms, known as microfilariae (Mf), are transmitted between humans by mosquitoes. LF is endemic in 55 countries and is targeted for elimination as a public health problem by the World Health Organization (WHO).[1] The main strategy to prevent transmission is mass drug administration (MDA) using albendazole, diethylcarbamazine and ivermectin in a two drug combination based on the presence of other endemic pathogens.[2]

Diethylcarbamazine and albendazole, known as DA, has been the standard combination used in Pacific countries. The efficacy of a single round of DA as measured by the clearance of Mf ranges from 7–76% at 12 months, 46–66% at 24 months and 83% at 36 months.[3-6] Given the wide range of efficacy at 12 months, multiple annual treatments are recommended to achieve community clearance.[7-9] This approach has been successful in reaching elimination targets in a number of countries, but not in others even after multiple rounds.[1]

LF remains endemic in specific areas in Fiji despite many years of control efforts.[1]

Complications of the infection were reported from Fiji as early as 1841,[10] and the first national survey in the 1940s observed a Mf prevalence of 12.7%.[11] National MDA with diethylcarbamazine was first introduced in 1969,[12] after mosquito control strategies had failed to reduce filariasis levels.[13, 14] The national program has adopted DA since 2002.

Co-administration of ivermectin with DA, known as IDA, has been evaluated in individually randomised trials in Papua New Guinea and Cote d'Ivoire. In Papua New Guinea, one round of IDA was superior to DA in clearing Mf with efficacy of at least 96% at 12, 24 and 36

months.[3, 15] In Cote d'Ivoire, efficacy was 71-87% at 12 months and 61% at 24 months after a single IDA treatment.[16, 17] A large collaborative trial in Fiji, Haiti, India, Indonesia, and Papua New Guinea, found that community-wide IDA was as safe as DA,[18-20] leading to its adoption for LF elimination programs in certain settings.[21] The superiority of IDA over DA for Mf clearance at 12 months has been reported from the trial sites in Haiti, India and Papua New Guinea with IDA efficacy ranging from 84-96% compared to DA efficacy of 62-83%.[20, 22, 23] However, all these countries have nocturnal periodic LF transmitted by *Culex* and *Anopheles* vectors, while Fiji has transmission which is diurnally subperiodic transmitted by *Culex* and multiple species of *Aedes* mosquitos.[24] Here we report on the 12- and 24-month individual efficacy and the 12-month impact on community LF prevalence of IDA in Fiji.

Methods

Study design

We conducted a three-arm, cluster randomised, open-label safety and efficacy trial involving the whole populations of two Fijian islands, Rotuma and Gau (Figure 1).[19] These islands are within the Eastern Division of Fiji, which has had the highest prevalence of filarial antigenemia.[25] A survey in 2013, after 9 rounds of MDA, found prevalence of 10.5% in Rotuma and 1.6% in Gau (unpublished data, Fiji Centre for Communicable Disease Control).

Figure 1. Map of island study sites, village locations and treatment allocation

DA: diethylcarbamazine and albendazole; IDA1: ivermectin one dose, diethylcarbamazine and albendazole; IDA2: ivermectin two doses, diethylcarbamazine and albendazole

The study protocol (Supplementary protocol) was approved by the Royal Children's Hospital Melbourne Human Research Ethics Committee (reference 36205) and Fiji National Health Research and Ethics Review Committee (reference 2016.81.MC).[19]

Participants

Community engagement with an interactive presentation explaining the study was undertaken in each village. All residents of Rotuma and Gau were invited to their village central meeting place to participate at baseline and 12 month visits.

To measure the prevalence of LF in the entire community 12 months after MDA, people who had not been present at baseline were eligible to be enrolled at 12 months.

To further increase our understanding of Mf clearance in infected individuals from Rotuma, a selective third enrolment took place at 24 months on Rotuma only. Participants with a previous Mf positive blood smear (at either baseline or 12 months) were eligible.

Written consent was required from all participants and/or guardian. A unique identifier was used to link visits.

Randomisation and blinding

Randomisation was at the village level. All 35 villages on both islands agreed to participate (17 on Rotuma and 18 on Gau). Randomisation was generated and allocated using Stata software by an independent statistician in a 1:1:1 ratio stratified by island to either DA, IDA1 or IDA2 (IDA at enrolment and a second dose of ivermectin on day 8). The IDA2 group was included to compare the effect of one versus two doses of ivermectin on community prevalence of scabies. Participants and the study team were unblinded to treatment allocated and received.

Procedures

Prior to receiving medication, participants 2 years and older were tested for filarial infection. The presence of circulating filarial antigen (CFA) was first tested by placing 75 µl of capillary blood onto the rapid test, Alere Filariasis Test Strip (FTS, Alere Scarborough, Inc., Scarborough, ME, USA). CFA positivity was determined by comparing the colour strength of the test line against the control at 10 minutes, to give a score of 0 (negative); 1 (weak

positive); 2 (medium positive); or 3 (strong positive).[26] If participants had a negative CFA result they were assumed to be Mf negative. If participants had a positive CFA result (score 1-3), they had a test for Mf by light microscopy of a 60 µl stained capillary blood smear.[9] Smears were read independently by two laboratory technicians, with the average count recorded.[9, 27] Smears with a count discrepancy of more than 10% were re-counted. Mf density estimates per ml were calculated by using the Mf count from the smear and multiplying by 16.7.[9]

Exclusion criteria for treatment were age less than 2 years, weight under 15kg, pregnancy, breastfeeding within 7 days of delivery, severe illness, or allergy to study medications. Participants aged less than 5 years were also excluded from taking ivermectin in the IDA arm.

Trial drugs were offered at the end of the baseline visit and administered under direct observation in standard doses based on body weight for ivermectin 200µg/kg and diethylcarbamazine (6mg/kg) and as a fixed 400mg dose for albendazole (Supplementary Table 2).

After assessment at 12 and 24 months, all participants were treated with IDA, the new nationally recommended regimen based on updated WHO guidelines,[21] according to the same dosing and exclusion criteria at baseline.

Statistical analysis

We estimated that the Mf prevalence at baseline would be 1%, equating to at least 13 Mf positive individuals in each study arm of 1300 enrolled participants. This sample size would

provide 80% power to detect superiority of the IDA regimen, based on data from a pilot study that found 90% reduction in Mf prevalence after IDA and 60% reduction after DA.[3] A second dose of ivermectin one week after IDA was not expected to change the effect of treatment on adult worms or microfilariae. We therefore combined IDA1 and IDA2 in the analysis, and compared to DA.

For analyses of efficacy of Mf and CFA clearance at 12 months, only participants who were Mf positive and CFA positive respectively at baseline, received treatment, and had filariasis testing at 12 months were included. For 24-month Mf clearance analysis, participants were only from Rotuma and also required treatment at 12 months and testing at 24 months.

Participants were grouped according to baseline village randomisation. To analyse treatment effect on Mf clearance, we used generalised linear modelling with a log link and binomial distribution, adjusted for clustering by village and stratification by island at 12 months, and for village clustering at 24 months. When assessing other potential contributing factors (island, sex, age, CFA score and village treatment coverage) on Mf clearance, we did not adjust for stratification by island because models did not converge. We used linear regression adjusted for clustering by village and stratified by island for analysis of the effect of Mf density and medication dose. Comparison of change of CFA semi-quantitative scores from baseline to 12 months was done using Pearson's chi-square test.

To assess impact of MDA on community prevalence of LF, the denominator for prevalence calculations was the number of participants tested at each timepoint. Participants were assigned the treatment allocation of the village where they were resident at each timepoint, regardless of treatment they received. Point estimates with 95% confidence intervals (CI) at each timepoint were adjusted for clustering by village and stratification by island. To calculate absolute reduction in community prevalence we subtracted 12-month prevalence

from baseline prevalence for every village. Risk ratios were calculated using generalised linear models with binomial distribution and log link that adjusted for clustering by village, stratification by island and baseline prevalence. We used linear regression using cluster level summaries of prevalence to assess the effect of treatment, treatment coverage, baseline prevalence, sex and island residence on Mf prevalence at 12 months.

Data were analysed using Stata software version 14.2. The trial was prospectively registered (Clinitrials.gov NCT03177993 and ANZCTR N12617000738325).

Results

Baseline visits took place from 13th July to 14th November, 2017, 12-month visits from 24th July to 19th November, 2018, and 24-month visit to Rotuma only from 19th to 24th October, 2019. We had 82% enrolment coverage for baseline and 12-months (Table 1, Figure 2), with age and sex of participants representative of overall population distribution (Supplementary Tables 3–5. At the 24-month visit, 92 of 131 eligible Mf positive participants from Rotuma re-enrolled (Supplementary Figure 5).

Table 1. Population coverage for enrolment and lymphatic filariasis mass drug administration at baseline and 12 months

Study Group	Level of participation	Coverage at baseline		Coverage at 12 months	
		n	% of census	n	% of census
DA	Census population	1616		1679	
	Enrolled	1293	80.0	1423	84.8
	Received LF MDA	1216	75.2	1324	78.9
IDA	Census population	2994		3073	
	Enrolled	2519	84.1	2475	80.5
	Received LF MDA	2396	80.0	2344	76.3
All groups	Census population	4610 ^a		4752 ^b	
	Enrolled	3812	82.7	3898	82.0
	Received LF MDA ^c	3612	78.4	3668	77.2

DA: diethylcarbamazine and albendazole; IDA: ivermectin, diethylcarbamazine and albendazole; LF: lymphatic filariasis; MDA: mass drug administration

^a Baseline census population: Rotuma N=1994; Gau N=2616; Median village N=108 (range 18–298); Median household N=5.

^b 12-month census population: Rotuma N=2112; Gau N=2640; Median village N=125 (range 17–310); Median household N=6.

^c Treatment coverage by village ranged from 54.4–100% at baseline and 56.4–88.8% at 12 months (Supplementary Table 4).

Figure 2. Trial profile detailing village cluster randomisation, enrolment and treatment at baseline and enrolment at 12-month follow-up

DA: diethylcarbamazine and albendazole; IDA1: ivermectin one dose, diethylcarbamazine and albendazole; IDA2: ivermectin two doses, diethylcarbamazine and albendazole; LF: lymphatic filariasis; MDA: mass drug administration; y: years; kg: kilograms

^a Treatment was provided as per village randomisation except for one person in the DA group who received IDA and 123 in the IDA groups who received DA (due to ineligibility for ivermectin because of weight and/or age). 61 moved between DA and IDA village treatment assignments at 12 months.

^b Of the 525 who declined participation at 12 months, 284 (54%) had previously participated, 159 (30.3%) had previously declined, and 82 (15.6%) were present for the first time and declined.

At baseline, CFA screening was performed for 3659 (98.4%) of the eligible 3719 participants aged 2 years and older, and at the 12-month visit, CFA screening was performed for 3773 (99.7%) of eligible 3786 participants (Supplementary Figure 2). There were 2816 participants who completed CFA screening at baseline and 12 months. Sixty-six participants who were positive for Mf at baseline were tested and treated at all three timepoints (Supplementary Table 11 and Supplementary Figure 7).

Baseline filariasis infection characteristics were similar in all three treatment groups (14.1% positive for CFA, 3.8% positive for Mf with a geometric mean Mf density of 198 per ml (range 17–9168, Figures 3–4, Supplementary Tables 6–9).[19] Mf prevalence was highest in males and adults aged 35–49 years (Supplementary Figures 3 and 8). Rotuma had Mf positive individuals in 88.2% of villages with village prevalence range 0–19.3%, compared to Gau with Mf positive individuals in 61.1% villages and prevalence range 0–9.2% (Supplementary Table 8 and Supplementary Figure 4). A majority of Mf positive participants on Gau were from one village randomised to DA, with only a few participants with Mf in villages randomised to IDA (Supplementary Tables 7–8).

Figure 3. Individual efficacy of different treatments on lymphatic filariasis comparing baseline to 12 months and grouped by baseline village randomisation*

DA: diethylcarbamazine and albendazole, N=39; IDA1: ivermectin one dose, diethylcarbamazine and albendazole, N=35; IDA2: ivermectin two doses, diethylcarbamazine and albendazole, N=37; Microfilarial density: a log of the estimate microfilariae density in one millilitre of blood

* Increased Mf density at 12 months in N=10 (9%); DA n=3 (7.7%); IDA n=7 (9.7%); geometric mean Mf density changing from 53 (range 17–434) Mf/ml, to 143 (33–451) Mf/ml).

Figure 4. Change in semi-quantitative circulating filarial antigen score over time by treatment group

DA: diethylcarbamazine and albendazole; IDA: ivermectin, diethylcarbamazine and albendazole; CFA score: circulating filarial antigen semi-quantification score – 0=negative, 1=weak positive, 2=medium positive, 3=strong positive; 12m: 12-month follow-up

^a Frequency is a percentage of total of those CFA positive at baseline, treated and a score recorded at 12 months (N=380); increased score n=7 (1.8%, 0.7% DA versus 2.5% IDA); no change in score n=109 (28.7%, 25.7% DA versus 30.5% IDA).

Clearance of LF infection in individuals

At the 12-month visit, 111 of the 139 (79.9%) Mf positive participants who received treatment at baseline were re-tested. Clearance was achieved in 72 individuals (64.9%, 95% CI 51.7–76.1%), with Mf clearance by village that ranged from 33.3–100%, and there was no significant difference between treatment groups (DA 69.2% versus IDA 62.5%, $P = 0.30$, Table 2, Supplementary Table 6). There was a reduction in mean Mf density in all three treatment groups (Supplementary Table 6). The baseline geometric mean density of Mf was more than three times higher in participants who did not achieve Mf clearance compared to

those who did (444 vs 128 Mf/ml, $p < 0.001$). There was no difference in the mean dose per kg weight of medication received between those who did and did not achieve Mf clearance (DEC 5.9 versus 5.7mg/kg respectively, $P = 0.16$; ivermectin 195.8 versus 191.5mcg/kg respectively, $P = 0.33$). Participants aged 65 years and older were more likely to clear Mf compared to those aged 35–49 years, as were participants from Gau compared to Rotuma (Table 3). Sex and CFA score were not associated with improved Mf clearance (Table 3). Village treatment coverage was also not associated with Mf clearance, $P = 0.37$.

Table 2. Efficacy of different treatments on clearance of circulating filarial antigen and microfilariae at 12 months

Measure of infection	Treatment	Positive baseline	Negative 12 months ^c	Rate of clearance		Risk difference ^d		P value
		Number of participants	Number of participants	%	(95% CI) ^d	%	(95% CI)	
Mf clearance ^a	DA	39	27	69.2	(57.2-79.1)	Control		0.30
	IDA	72	45	62.5	(43.6-78.2)	11.3	(-10.0 to 32.7)	
CFA clearance ^b	DA	144	67	46.5	(30.7-63.1)	Control		0.71
	IDA	236	86	36.4	(29.8-43.7)	-3.1	(-19.5 to 13.3)	

DA: diethylcarbamazine and albendazole; IDA: ivermectin, diethylcarbamazine and albendazole; Mf: microfilarial; CFA: circulating filarial antigen; CI: confidence intervals

^a Excludes n=1 in DA group not treated

^b Excludes n=2 in DA group and n=1 in IDA group not treated

^c Participants grouped according to baseline randomisation and treatment and not village residency at 12-month visit

^d Adjusted for clustering by village and stratification by island

Table 3. Factors associated with clearance of microfilariae

Factor	Group	Mf positive baseline	Mf negative 12 months	%	Univariate analysis ^a	
					Risk difference %	(95% CI)
Island	Rotuma	84	49	58.3	Ref	
	Gau	27	23	85.2	35.1	(16.6-53.5)
Gender	Male	90	55	61.1	Ref	
	Female	21	17	81.0	19.0	(-0.6-38.6)
Age (years)	5-24	8	5	62.5	1.3	(-24.2-26.9)
	25-34	15	11	73.3	10.5	(-9.8-30.9)
	35-49	42	26	61.9	Ref	
	50-64	30	16	53.3	-8.6	(-31.7-14.4)
	≥65	16	14	87.5	24.7	(2.1-47.3)
LF	CFA1 - weak positive	6	5	83.3	Ref	
	CFA2 - medium positive	23	19	82.6	-3.6	(-41.7-34.5)
	CFA3 - strong positive	82	48	58.5	-27.8	(-64.0-8.4)

DA: diethylcarbamazine and albendazole; IDA: ivermectin, diethylcarbamazine and albendazole; LF: lymphatic filariasis; CFA: circulating filarial antigen; Mf: microfilariae; CI: confidence intervals

^a Generalised linear modelling adjusting for clustering by village, denominator n=111.

There was no difference between treatment groups in changes in CFA score at 12 months, $P = 0.23$ (Figure 4). Of 380 who were positive for CFA at baseline and received treatment, the majority (n=264, 69.5%) had a reduction in their CFA score with 153 (40.3%) negative for CFA at 12 months, Table 2.

Of the 92 participants tested at 24 months, 84 (91.3%) were CFA positive, and 53 (58.2%) had cleared Mf based on 3-line blood smear testing (Supplementary Figure 6). In the 66 participants with data at all three timepoints, Mf clearance at 24 months was achieved in 12/15 (80%) who were treated with DA at baseline and IDA at 12 months, and 27/51 (52.9%) who received IDA at both baseline and 12 months ($P = 0.017$, Supplementary Table 11). In

the 27 participants positive for Mf at 24 months, there was a decrease in the geometric mean Mf density over time that was similar between treatment groups (Supplementary Table 13). Of the 24 participants who tested positive for Mf at baseline and 12 months, 6 (25%) were Mf negative at 24 months (Supplementary Table 12). Of the 10 participants positive for Mf at baseline and not treated at 12 months, 2 were negative at 24 months (Supplementary Table 14).

Change in community prevalence of Mf

At 12 months, the overall prevalence of Mf in the study population had decreased, with no statistical difference between treatment groups (adjusted absolute reduction DA 1.6%, 95% CI 0.7–5.2% versus IDA 1.3%, 0.1–2.5%, $P = 0.68$, Table 4, Supplementary Figure 8). Similarly, there was no statistical difference between treatment groups in the reduction of community CFA prevalence at 12 months (adjusted absolute reduction DA 6.9%, 95% CI 4.4-9.3% versus IDA 4.6%, 2.6-6.5%, $P = 0.10$, Table 4, Supplementary Figure 8).

Table 4. Effectiveness of different treatments on community prevalence of lymphatic filariasis at 12 months

Measure of infection	Treatment	Prevalence at baseline ^c				Prevalence at 12 months ^c				Absolute reduction ^d		Risk ratio ^e	
		N	n	%	(95% CI)	N	n	%	(95% CI)	%	(95% CI)	%	(95% CI)
Mf positive ^a	DA	1238	47	3.8	(1.5-9.1)	1372	26	1.9	(0.7-5.2)	1.6	(0.3-2.9)	1	(ref)
	IDA	2399	93	3.9	(2.6-5.8)	2398	46	1.9	(1.0-3.6)	1.3	(0.1-2.5)	0.8	(0.5-1.3)
CFA positive ^b	DA	1239	186	15.0	(8.8-24.4)	1372	109	7.9	(3.5-17.1)	6.9	(4.4-9.3)	1	(ref)
	IDA	2420	330	13.6	(10.0-18.3)	2401	211	8.8	(6.2-12.3)	4.6	(2.6-6.5)	1.1	(0.8-1.4)

DA: diethylcarbamazine and albendazole; IDA: ivermectin, diethylcarbamazine and albendazole; CFA: circulating filarial antigen; Mf: microfilariae; CI: confidence intervals; Ref: reference group

^a Mf denominator Baseline N=3637 excludes n=71 declined, n=93 ineligible, n=11 unreadable; 12 months N=3770 excludes n=15 declined, n=112 ineligible, n=1 unreadable; participants are grouped into the village randomisation they were resident at time of testing; N=225 Mf smears both timepoints; N=286 baseline only; N=93 12 months only.

^b CFA denominator Baseline N=3659 excludes n=60 declined, n=93 ineligible; 12 months N=3773 excludes n=13 declined, n=112 ineligible; participants are grouped into the village randomisation they were resident at time of testing; N=2816 tested at both timepoints, N=843 tested at baseline only; N=957 tested at 12 months only.

^c Adjusted for clustering on village and stratified by island; Mf positive at 12 months N=72 (n=40 Mf positive at baseline, n=11 Mf negative or Mf unknown at baseline, and n=21 absent at baseline); CFA positive at 12 months for the first time N=91 (n=17 previously CFA negative, n=1 not eligible for testing at baseline, and n=73 absent at baseline).

^d Adjusted for clustering on village

^e Adjusted for clustering by village, stratified by island and baseline Mf prevalence

High baseline community Mf prevalence was associated with a higher community Mf prevalence at 12 months, $p < 0.001$. There was no effect observed for village treatment allocation ($P = 0.63$), treatment coverage ($P = 0.52$), or sex ($P = 0.25$).

Discussion

In the first reported comparison of IDA versus DA in a setting of diurnally subperiodic LF, we found no difference in individual clearance of Mf at 12 months between groups.

Similarly, there was no added benefit of IDA on community Mf prevalence at 12 months.

The efficacy of both treatments for Mf clearance at 12 months was comparable to the highest reported efficacy for DA.[6] Among participants from Rotuma positive for Mf 12 months

after the first round of treatment, we did not observe an increased level of clearance 12 months after a second round of IDA.

Our findings contrast with previous reports of superior efficacy of IDA compared to DA. There are several possible explanations for the apparent lesser effect of IDA in our study, broadly divided into factors that may contribute to reduced clearance in individuals or reinfection.

Clearance of infection is related to choice of medication, host and parasite factors. All medications were sourced from reputable sources and stored at recommended temperatures, and administered under direct observation at adequate doses by weight. Our study population had a higher mean BMI compared to other countries in the IDA community trials,[28] however body fat percentage has not been shown to affect ivermectin pharmacokinetics.[29] Diet may have altered the absorption and/or metabolism of the medications, but we would expect this to be a random effect balanced across treatment groups.[30] The population of Rotuma, a very remote island in the Pacific, may have host genetic factors that contribute to altered metabolism, and hence reduced efficacy of the medications.[31] Ivermectin is not widely available in Fiji, so parasite resistance to ivermectin as a result of human consumption is unlikely. It is possible for sub-populations of adult *W. bancrofti* that form worm nests within infected individuals to be resistant to treatment, as observed in Brazil and Cote d'Ivoire.[17, 32] This could explain our observation of reduced geometric mean Mf density without clearance, and the reduced Mf clearance after a second round of IDA in individuals who failed to clear after the first round of treatment.

Reinfection is possible in this high prevalence setting, supported by evidence of ongoing transmission with new infections appearing in children. There are several potential factors to

explain why participants in our study may have had a higher likelihood of reinfection compared to populations included in other IDA efficacy studies. First, individuals in Fiji are at risk of exposure to parasite-carrying mosquitos throughout both day and night because filariasis is diurnally subperiodic.[33] Second, the predominant *Aedes* mosquito in Fiji has the ability to efficiently transmit the parasite following a blood meal when Mf density is low in the human host.[24, 34] Third, there are no vector control interventions (e.g. long-lasting insecticide treated bed nets) implemented as public health strategies for LF control in Fiji, in contrast to Papua New Guinea and Cote d'Ivoire that have nocturnal LF transmission and active bed net programs for malaria control. In other countries with diurnally subperiodic LF, the strategy of MDA without addressing vector control has been cautioned.[35]

There are several strengths of our study. First, we are confident that oral study medications were administered because they were provided as directly observed therapy. Second, loss to follow up was very low, specifically among Mf positive participants. Third, the same laboratory technician read all smears at all timepoints eliminating inter-reader variability of Mf counts. There are also limitations of our study. First, it was not possible to blind our participants or assessors to treatment randomisation. Second, the baseline prevalence of LF differed between treatment groups on Gau, an island with overall low prevalence. There had been no recent comprehensive island LF surveys conducted, so we were not able to accurately predict and account for high prevalence localities in the randomisation. Many of the Mf positive participants on Gau lived in a single village randomised to DA, and this limited the reliability of any inter-island treatment effect comparisons. Third, treatment randomisation of clusters rather than individuals or households, may not have eliminated the possibility of residual confounding.

Scrotal ultrasounds have been used to detect and monitor the impact of medications on worm nests.[16, 17] This technique may have helped to distinguish between failure to clear infections present at baseline and re-infection over the course of the study. Similarly, molecular xenomonitoring of mosquitos for filarial DNA may have provided additional information on transmission dynamics in our villages. Utilisation of these tools could enhance our understanding of the impact on individuals and communities in future implementation of MDA and transmission assessments.

Despite the finding in our study that the reduction in community burden of LF at 12 months was comparable between treatment groups, successive rounds of MDA remain a valuable strategy to achieve a reduction in community prevalence of LF. The addition of ivermectin to DA, while not adding benefit for filariasis control in our study, has the potential to impact other neglected tropical diseases, notably scabies and soil-transmitted helminths.[2, 36-39] Seeking treatment for these symptomatic infections may motivate participation in successive rounds of MDA and lead to increased success for LF control.

Our findings emphasize the importance of multi-centre, community-based studies in varied settings, including those with diurnally subperiodic transmission by predominantly Aedine vectors. Repeating IDA efficacy studies in other areas with diurnally subperiodic LF will be important to better understand the reasons for our findings. Our study will influence policy decision-making in Fiji, and potentially in other settings with similar transmission dynamics, regarding the number of MDA rounds needed to achieve elimination, and community messaging alongside these new policies. Ultimately, further research into different strategies in different settings remains crucial to achieving elimination of filariasis around the world.

Notes

Author contributions

MH, JS, ACS, GJW, CLK, JMK and LJR contributed to the design of the study. MH was the primary coordinator of data collection, analysis and primary author of the manuscript. ACS, JMK and LJR supervised data collection, analysis, interpretation and manuscript writing. Fieldwork was supported by JS, MK, MT, LR and MJW. ACG supported data analysis. All authors contributed to the writing of the manuscript and approved the final version.

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Disclaimer

The funders of this study had no role in the study design, data collection, analysis and interpretation, or writing of the report. The corresponding author had full access to the complete dataset and had final responsibility for the decision to submit for publication.

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Potential conflicts of interest

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Supplementary Table 1. CONSORT 2010 checklist of information to include when reporting a cluster randomised trial

Section/Topic	Item No	Standard Checklist item	Extension for cluster designs	Page No
Title and abstract				
	1a	Identification as a randomised trial in the title	Identification as a cluster randomised trial in the title	1
	1b	Structured summary of trial design, methods, results, and conclusions (for specific guidance see CONSORT for abstracts)	See table 2	3-5
Introduction				
Background and objectives	2a	Scientific background and explanation of rationale	Rationale for using a cluster design	7-8
	2b	Specific objectives or hypotheses	Whether objectives pertain to the cluster level, the individual participant level or both	7
Methods				
Trial design	3a	Description of trial design (such as parallel, factorial) including allocation ratio	Definition of cluster and description of how the design features apply to the clusters	7-8
	3b	Important changes to methods after trial commencement (such as eligibility criteria), with reasons		N/A
Participants	4a	Eligibility criteria for participants	Eligibility criteria for clusters	7-8
	4b	Settings and locations where the data were collected		7, Fig 1
Interventions	5	The interventions for each group with sufficient details to allow replication, including how and when they were actually administered	Whether interventions pertain to the cluster level, the individual participant level or both	8-10, Supp Table 2, Supp Fig 1
Outcomes	6a	Completely defined pre-specified primary and secondary outcome measures, including how and when they were assessed	Whether outcome measures pertain to the cluster level, the individual participant level or both	10-14
	6b	Any changes to trial outcomes after the trial commenced, with reasons		N/A
Sample size	7a	How sample size was determined	Method of calculation, number of clusters(s) (and whether equal or unequal cluster sizes are assumed), cluster size, a coefficient of intracluster correlation (ICC or k), and an indication of its uncertainty	10
	7b	When applicable, explanation of any interim analyses and stopping guidelines		N/A

Randomisation:				
Sequence generation	8a	Method used to generate the random allocation sequence		8
	8b	Type of randomisation; details of any restriction (such as blocking and block size)	Details of stratification or matching if used	8
Allocation concealment mechanism	9	Mechanism used to implement the random allocation sequence (such as sequentially numbered containers), describing any steps taken to conceal the sequence until interventions were assigned	Specification that allocation was based on clusters rather than individuals and whether allocation concealment (if any) was at the cluster level, the individual participant level or both	8
Implementation	10	Who generated the random allocation sequence, who enrolled participants, and who assigned participants to interventions	Replace by 10a, 10b and 10c	
	10a		Who generated the random allocation sequence, who enrolled clusters, and who assigned clusters to interventions	8
	10b		Mechanism by which individual participants were included in clusters for the purposes of the trial (such as complete enumeration, random sampling)	8
	10c		From whom consent was sought (representatives of the cluster, or individual cluster members, or both), and whether consent was sought before or after randomisation	8
Blinding	11a	If done, who was blinded after assignment to interventions (for example, participants, care providers, those assessing outcomes) and how		N/A
	11b	If relevant, description of the similarity of interventions		N/A
Statistical methods	12a	Statistical methods used to compare groups for primary and secondary outcomes	How clustering was taken into account	10-11
	12b	Methods for additional analyses, such as subgroup analyses and adjusted analyses		10-11
Results				
Participant flow (a diagram is	13a	For each group, the numbers of participants who were randomly assigned, received intended	For each group, the numbers of clusters that were randomly assigned, received intended	Fig 2

strongly recommended)		treatment, and were analysed for the primary outcome	treatment, and were analysed for the primary outcome	
	13b	For each group, losses and exclusions after randomisation, together with reasons	For each group, losses and exclusions for both clusters and individual cluster members	Fig 2, Supp Fig 2, 5 & 6
Recruitment	14a	Dates defining the periods of recruitment and follow-up		11
	14b	Why the trial ended or was stopped		N/A
Baseline data	15	A table showing baseline demographic and clinical characteristics for each group	Baseline characteristics for the individual and cluster levels as applicable for each group	11-14, Fig 3 & 4, Supp Tables 3, 5, 7-9
Numbers analysed	16	For each group, number of participants (denominator) included in each analysis and whether the analysis was by original assigned groups	For each group, number of clusters included in each analysis	11-14, Table 1, Fig 2, Supp Fig 2
Outcomes and estimation	17a	For each primary and secondary outcome, results for each group, and the estimated effect size and its precision (such as 95% confidence interval)	Results at the individual or cluster level as applicable and a coefficient of intracluster correlation (ICC or k) for each primary outcome	12-14, Tables 2 & 4, Fig 3-4, Supp Tables 6-14
	17b	For binary outcomes, presentation of both absolute and relative effect sizes is recommended		12-14, Tables 2 & 4, Fig 3-4, Supp Tables 6-14
Ancillary analyses	18	Results of any other analyses performed, including subgroup analyses and adjusted analyses, distinguishing pre-specified from exploratory		12-14, Table 3, Supp Tables 6-14, Supp Fig 3-8
Harms	19	All important harms or unintended effects in each group (for specific guidance see CONSORT for harms)		Ref 19
Discussion				
Limitations	20	Trial limitations, addressing sources of potential bias, imprecision, and, if relevant, multiplicity of analyses		16
Generalisability	21	Generalisability (external validity, applicability) of the trial findings	Generalisability to clusters and/or individual participants (as relevant)	14-17
Interpretation	22	Interpretation consistent with results, balancing benefits and harms, and considering other relevant evidence		14-17

Other information			
Registration	23	Registration number and name of trial registry	11
Protocol	24	Where the full trial protocol can be accessed, if available	Supp Protocol
Funding	25	Sources of funding and other support (such as supply of drugs), role of funders	19

Supplementary Table 2. Medication dosing schedule

Medication dosing schedule (by weight or age)	
Albendazole	
≥ 15 kg	1 tablet (400 mg)
Diethylcarbamazine	(dosing 6mg/kg)
15-25 kg	1 tablet (100 mg)
26-41 kg	2 tablets (200 mg)
42-58 kg	3 tablets (300 mg)
59-75 kg	4 tablets (400 mg)
76-92 kg	5 tablets (500 mg)
≥ 93 kg	6 tablets (600 mg)
Ivermectin	(dosing 200 µg/kg)
15-23 kg	1 tablet (3 mg)
24-38 kg	2 tablets (6 mg)
39-53 kg	3 tablets (9 mg)
54-68 kg	4 tablets (12 mg)
69-83 kg	5 tablets (15 mg)
84-98 kg	6 tablets (18 mg)
≥ 99 kg	7 tablets (21 mg)
Permethrin	(dosing topical 5%)
Age < 2 months	Apply for 4 hours
Age ≥ 2 months	Apply for 8 hours

Supplementary Table 3. Baseline population and participant demographics, and LF MDA coverage by village

Village ^a	Population demographics					Participant demographics					LF MDA coverage		
	Total	Male		Age		Total	Male		Age		n	% of census	
	N	n	%	Median	IQR	N	%	n	%	Median			IQR
DA													
2	18	9	50	52.5	15-65	18	100.0	9	50.0	52.5	15-65	18	100.0
3	204	106	52	31	11-48.5	167	81.9	81	48.5	26	10-48	159	77.9
4	107	54	50.5	35	10-53	84	78.5	43	51.2	31.5	9-48	82	76.6
8	102	51	50	43.5	14-60	78	76.5	38	48.7	42.5	13-57	73	71.6
16	98	46	46.9	29	11-51	86	87.8	41	47.7	27	10-49	80	81.6
18	253	132	52.2	25	9-38	215	85.0	111	51.6	22	9-37	202	79.8
26	297	159	53.5	23	11-48	266	89.6	135	50.8	22	10-48	252	84.8
29	298	160	53.7	22	9-42	169	56.7	96	56.8	21	9-41	162	54.4
30	75	35	46.7	36	24-54	67	89.3	32	47.8	36	23-55	57	76.0
32	118	71	60.2	31.5	10-53	106	89.8	64	60.4	27.5	10-50	97	82.2
34	46	29	63	32	21-53	37	80.4	23	62.2	36	21-55	34	73.9
Total DA	1616	852	52.7	28.5	11-49	1293	80.0	673	52	27	10-48	1216	75.2
IDA1													
6	79	40	50.6	38	12-55	67	84.8	35	52.2	33	10-53	66	83.5
7	66	37	56.1	31.5	13-44	47	71.2	27	57.4	23	11-40	46	69.7
10	240	129	53.8	31	12.5-52	204	85.0	109	53.4	29	12-50	199	82.9
13	73	31	42.5	44	16-69	59	80.8	25	42.4	36	13-55	58	79.5
15	151	73	48.3	31	13-52	126	83.4	64	50.8	24	12-46	123	81.5
17	86	49	57	30	12-51	78	90.7	46	59.0	23.5	12-49	75	87.2
19	99	59	59.6	25	10-44	84	84.8	47	56.0	22.5	9-42.5	78	78.8
22	139	66	47.5	31	8-52	116	83.5	49	42.2	31	8-51	107	77.0
24	45	26	57.8	38	29-53	40	88.9	23	57.5	42.5	29.5-59	36	80.0
25	92	41	44.6	31	8-51	75	81.5	34	45.3	20	8-50	71	77.2
27	146	74	50.7	26	9-45	127	87.0	62	48.8	23	9-44	115	78.8
35	160	78	48.8	16	15-18	159	99.4	78	49.1	16	15-18	156	97.5
Total IDA1	1376	703	51.1	26	12-49	1182	85.9	599	50.7	22	11-46	1130	82.1
IDA2													
1	107	57	53.3	24	10-37	88	82.2	47	53.4	16	9-36	87	81.3
5	224	120	53.6	32	11-52	180	80.4	97	53.9	27	11-48.5	177	79.0
9	60	31	51.7	33	10-52.5	48	80.0	25	52.1	20	9-47	48	80.0
11	197	94	47.7	32	12-52	141	71.6	63	44.7	26	10-47	136	69.0
12	142	70	49.3	34.5	17-60	114	80.3	52	45.6	31.5	14-59	108	76.1
14	40	23	57.5	41.5	14-55	32	80.0	20	62.5	20.5	10-52.5	31	77.5
20	108	57	52.8	21.5	10-44.5	90	83.3	46	51.1	18.5	8-43	85	78.7
21	101	52	51.5	33	9-48	78	77.2	39	50.0	28	7-45	70	69.3
23	142	77	54.2	26.5	9-45	127	89.4	71	55.9	20	8-42	115	81.0
28	172	92	53.5	28.5	8.5-43	146	84.9	80	54.8	29	10-43	135	78.5
31	198	104	52.5	27.5	10-47	178	89.9	96	53.9	22.5	9-45	169	85.4
33	127	63	49.6	20	8-46	115	90.6	58	50.4	19	8-46	105	82.7
Total IDA2	1618	840	51.9	29	10-49	1337	82.6	694	51.9	25	9-46	1266	78.2
Total all	4610	2395	52.0	28	11-49	3812	82.7	1966	51.6	25	10-47	3612	78.4

DA: diethylcarbamazine and albendazole; IDA1: ivermectin one dose, diethylcarbamazine and albendazole; IDA2: ivermectin two dose with DA; IQR: interquartile range; MDA: mass drug administration

^a Villages 1-17 are on Rotuma; Villages 18-35 are on Gau; Median village size 108.

Supplementary Table 4. 12-month population and participant demographics, and LF MDA coverage by village

Village ^a	Population demographics					Participant demographics					LF MDA coverage			
	Total		Male		Age		Total		Male		Age		n	% of census
	N	n	%	Median	IQR	N	%	n	%	Median	IQR			
DA														
2	17	9	52.9	56	27-66	11	64.7	5	45.5	49	15-66	11	64.7	
3	222	121	54.5	28.5	12-49	163	73.4	86	52.8	19	10-45	155	69.8	
4	115	57	49.6	33	9-49	81	70.4	40	49.4	26	9-43	78	67.8	
8	108	50	46.3	38	13.5-56	82	75.9	37	45.1	39	11-55	75	69.4	
16	102	50	49.0	30.5	11-52	89	87.3	44	49.4	29	11-47	82	80.4	
18	263	134	51.0	26	9-39	234	89.0	118	50.4	24.5	8-38	216	82.1	
26	310	167	53.9	23	11-48	284	91.6	152	53.5	21.5	10.5-48.5	269	86.8	
29	299	159	53.2	25	10-43	258	86.3	139	53.9	23	9-44	250	83.6	
30	70	31	44.3	38	24-55	56	80.0	27	48.2	35.5	24-55	45	64.3	
32	132	84	63.6	28	10.5-51	126	95.5	81	64.3	28	10-51	111	84.1	
34	41	24	58.5	37	21-56	39	95.1	22	56.4	38	20-56	32	78.0	
Total DA	1679	886	52.8	29	11-49	1423	84.8	751	52.8	26	10-47	1324	78.9	
IDA1														
6	80	43	53.8	42	12-56	63	78.8	33	52.4	46	11-56	60	75.0	
7	69	36	52.2	28	13-45	51	73.9	26	51.0	24	11-41	50	72.5	
10	272	157	57.7	32	13-51	233	85.7	139	59.7	28	12-48	227	83.5	
13	66	28	42.4	46	14-64	52	78.8	24	46.2	32.5	13.5-53.5	50	75.8	
15	156	73	46.8	32	13-53	109	69.9	50	45.9	25	12-52	105	67.3	
17	98	52	53.1	18	9-45	89	90.8	47	52.8	16	9-40	81	82.7	
19	97	58	59.8	24	10-44	79	81.4	43	54.4	21	8-44	70	72.2	
22	125	64	51.2	31	9-51	119	95.2	59	49.6	31	9-51	111	88.8	
24	48	28	58.3	39	27-53.5	38	79.2	20	52.6	41	28-54	36	75.0	
25	94	44	46.8	30.5	9-51	82	87.2	38	46.3	21	9-47	76	80.9	
27	165	86	52.1	24	10-45	126	76.4	64	50.8	23.5	10-45	115	69.7	
35	173	82	47.4	17	15-19	155	89.6	74	47.7	16	15-19	150	86.7	
Total IDA1	1443	751	52	26	12-49	1196	82.9	617	51.6	23	11-47	1131	78.4	
IDA2														
1	175	126	72.0	27	19-37	132	75.4	106	80.3	27	21-37.5	129	73.7	
5	227	124	54.6	32	12-52	144	63.4	77	53.5	25.5	10.5-49	138	60.8	
9	45	24	53.3	39	12-58	30	66.7	13	43.3	29.5	11-53	30	66.7	
11	188	89	47.3	32.5	12-52	110	58.5	53	48.2	27.5	11-47	106	56.4	
12	136	66	48.5	41.5	18.5-60.5	96	70.6	44	45.8	47.5	18-61	93	68.4	
14	36	19	52.8	46	15-59	30	83.3	16	53.3	36.5	12-57	29	80.6	
20	125	67	53.6	22	9-45	111	88.8	59	53.2	23	9-45	103	82.4	
21	107	62	57.9	32	12-46	95	88.8	54	56.8	31	10-48	91	85.0	
23	127	70	55.1	30	9-46	112	88.2	64	57.1	27.5	8.5-44.5	101	79.5	
28	147	75	51.0	33	9-47	130	88.4	68	52.3	30.5	8-45	120	81.6	
31	206	100	48.5	24	8-44	195	94.7	92	47.2	22	8-44	183	88.8	
33	111	54	48.6	26	8-50	94	84.7	47	50.0	20	8-49	90	81.1	
Total IDA2	1630	876	53.7	30	11-49	1279	78.5	693	54.2	28	10-47	1213	74.4	
Total all	4752	2513	52.9	28	11-49	3898	82.0	2061	52.9	26	10-47	3668	77.2	

DA: diethylcarbamazine and albendazole; IDA1: ivermectin one dose, diethylcarbamazine and albendazole; IDA2: ivermectin two dose with DA; IQR: interquartile range; MDA: mass drug administration

^a Villages 1-17 are on Rotuma; Villages 18-35 are on Gau; Median village size 125.

Supplementary Table 5. Participant demographics at baseline and 12 months by village randomisation

	Village randomisation ^a															
	DA group				IDA1 group				IDA2 group				All groups			
	Baseline		12 months		Baseline		12 months		Baseline		12 months		Baseline		12 months	
	n	%	n	%	n	%	n	%	n	%	n	%	n	%	n	%
Population	161		167		137		144		161		163		4610		4752	
	6		9		6		3		8		0					
Consented	129	80.0	142	84.8	118	85.9	119	82.9	133	82.6	127	78.5	3812	82.7	3898	82.0
	3		3		2		6		7		9					
Sex																
Male	673	52.0	751	52.8	599	50.7	617	51.6	694	51.9	693	54.2	1966	51.6	2061	52.9
Female	620	48.0	672	47.2	583	49.3	579	48.4	643	48.1	586	45.8	1846	48.4	1837	47.1
Age (years)																
Med. (IQR)	27	(10-48)	26	(10-47)	22	(11-46)	23	(11-47)	25	(9-46)	28	(10-47)	25	(10-47)	26	(10-47)
<2	38	2.9	44	3.1	20	1.7	38	3.2	35	2.6	30	2.3	93	2.4	112	2.9
2-4	80	6.2	87	6.1	74	6.3	64	5.4	94	7.0	73	5.7	248	6.5	224	5.7
5-9	182	14.1	212	14.9	149	12.6	143	12.0	210	15.7	202	15.8	541	14.2	557	14.3
10-14	172	13.3	193	13.6	158	13.4	156	13.0	201	15.0	166	13.0	531	13.9	515	13.2
15-24	134	10.4	149	10.5	207	17.5	214	17.9	121	9.1	110	8.6	462	12.1	473	12.1
25-34	154	11.9	181	12.7	124	10.5	121	10.1	140	10.5	166	13.0	418	11.0	468	12.0
35-49	236	18.3	245	17.2	192	16.2	197	16.5	257	19.2	238	18.6	685	18.0	680	17.4
50-64	207	16.0	218	15.3	170	14.4	170	14.2	188	14.1	195	15.2	565	14.8	583	15.0
≥65	90	7.0	94	6.6	88	7.4	93	7.8	91	6.8	99	7.7	269	7.1	286	7.3

DA: diethylcarbamazine and albendazole; IDA1: ivermectin one dose, diethylcarbamazine and albendazole; IDA2: ivermectin two dose with DA; Med.: median; IQR: interquartile range

^a Participants are allocated to village randomisation group based on residence at each timepoint

Supplementary Table 6. Efficacy of treatment on microfilariae clearance and density by village

Village ^a	Mf clearance				Mf density				
	Positive baseline	Negative 12 months	Rate of clearance		Baseline		12 months		Absolute reduction
	N	n	%	(95% CI)	Geometric mean mf/ml ^b	Range	Geometric mean mf/ml ^b	Range	mf/ml
DA									
2	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
3	5	3	60.0	(14.7-94.7)	124	(50-735)	108	(100-117)	16
4	11	6	54.5	(23.4-83.3)	215	(17-4643)	183	(50-484)	32
8	3	2	66.7	(9.4-99.2)	151	(50-1035)	167	-	-16
16	1	1	100	(2.5-100) ^d	33	-	0	-	33
18	17	13	76.5	(50.1-93.2)	329	(17-4492)	56	(17-217)	273
26	1	1	100	(2.5-100) ^d	50	-	0	-	50
29	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
30	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
32	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
34	1	1	100	(2.5-100) ^d	601	-	0	-	601
Total DA^c	39	27	69.2	(57.2-79.1)	221	(17-4643)	112	(17-484)	109
IDA1									
6	5	3	60.0	(14.7-94.7)	109	(33-501)	17	(17-17)	92
7	2	1	50.0	(1.3-98.7)	65	(50-84)	17	-	48
10	6	6	100	(54.1-100) ^d	70	(17-234)	0	-	70
13	2	1	50.0	(1.3-98.7)	17	(17-17)	33	-	-16
15	4	3	75.0	(19.4-99.4)	85	(17-1253)	184	-	-99
17	10	4	40.0	(12.2-73.8)	196	(17-2271)	144	(67-351)	52
19	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
22	3	3	100	(29.2-100) ^d	197	(50-701)	0	-	197
24	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
25	2	2	100	(15.8-100) ^d	55	(17-184)	0	-	55
27	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
35	1	1	100	(2.5-100) ^d	334	-	0	-	334
Total IDA1^c	35	24	68.6	(43.8-85.9)	106	(17-2271)	72	(17-351)	34
IDA2									
1	1	1	100	(2.5-100) ^d	184	-	0	-	184
5	7	4	57.1	(18.4-90.1)	191	(17-768)	48	(17-100)	143
9	6	3	50.0	(11.8-88.2)	1005	(33-9168)	112	(33-501)	893
11	15	5	33.3	(11.8-61.6)	610	(33-5227)	123	(17-952)	487
12	6	6	100	(54.1-100) ^d	62	(17-251)	0	-	62
14	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
20	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
21	1	1	100	(2.5-100) ^d	33	-	0	-	33
23	1	1	100	(2.5-100) ^d	217	-	0	-	217
28	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
31	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
33	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Total IDA2^c	37	21	56.8	(31.4-79.0)	319	(17-9168)	101	(17-952)	218
Total all^c	111	72	64.9	(51.7-76.1)	198	(17-9168)	95	(17-952)	103

DA: diethylcarbamazine and albendazole; IDA1: ivermectin one dose, diethylcarbamazine and albendazole; IDA2: ivermectin two dose with DA; CI: confidence intervals

^a Villages 1-17 are on Rotuma; Villages 18-35 are on Gau; participants are grouped according to the village they were resident at baseline.

^b Geometric mean density excludes participants whose count was zero.

^c Adjusted for clustering on village and stratified by island

^d Confidence interval is one-sided, 97.5%

Supplementary Table 7. Baseline and 12-month filariasis infection prevalence by island

Measure of infection	Island Treatment	Prevalence at baseline ^c				Prevalence at 12 months ^c				Absolute reduction ^d		Risk ratio ^e	
		N	n	%	(95% CI)	N	n	%	(95% CI)	%	(95% CI)	%	(95% CI)
Mf + ^a	Total												
	DA	1238	47	3.8	(1.5-9.1)	1372	26	1.9	(0.7-5.2)	1.6	(0.3-2.9)	1	(ref)
	IDA1	1126	44	3.9	(2.3-6.6)	1156	21	1.8	(0.7-4.6)	1.5	(-0.59-3.6)	0.8	(0.4-1.5)
	IDA2	1273	49	3.8	(1.9-7.7)	1242	25	2.0	(0.7-5.3)	1.1	(-0.0-2.1)	0.8	(0.5-1.6)
	Rotuma												
	DA	418	25	6.0	(1.9-17.2)	412	17	4.1	(1.3-12.3)	1.8	(-0.4-3.9)	1	(ref)
	IDA1	548	36	6.6	(3.6-11.6)	582	21	3.6	(1.2-10.3)	1.7	(-2.7-6.2)	0.9	(0.5-1.8)
	IDA2	575	45	7.8	(4.7-12.7)	529	24	4.5	(1.7-11.3)	1.6	(-0.3-3.5)	1.0	(0.5-1.9)
	Gau												
	DA	820	22	2.7	(0.6-11.6)	960	9	0.9	(0.1-6.0)	1.5	(-0.3-3.3)	1	(ref)
	IDA1	578	8	1.4	(0.6-3.3)	574	0	0.0	-	1.3	(0.0-2.6)	-	-
	IDA2	698	4	0.6	(0.1-2.6)	713	1	0.1	(0.0-1.1)	0.5	(-0.6-1.6)	-	-
CFA + ^b	Total												
	DA	1239	186	15.0	(8.8-24.4)	1372	109	7.9	(3.5-17.1)	6.9	(4.4-9.3)	1	(ref)
	IDA1	1142	145	12.7	(8.5-18.5)	1157	99	8.6	(5.5-13.0)	3.6	(0.8-6.4)	1.1	(0.8-1.4)
	IDA2	1278	185	14.5	(8.3-24.0)	1244	112	9.0	(4.6-16.8)	5.6	(2.8-8.4)	1.0	(0.8-1.4)
	Rotuma												
	DA	419	113	27.0	(17.2-39.6)	412	70	17.0	(7.8-33.2)	8.1	(4.4-11.9)	1	(ref)
	IDA1	563	116	20.6	(16.4-25.5)	583	88	15.1	(10.5-21.2)	4.4	(-0.5-9.2)	1.1	(0.8-1.6)
	IDA2	580	159	27.4	(20.5-35.7)	531	97	18.3	(10.6-29.6)	8.9	(5.4-12.4)	1.1	(0.8-1.5)
	Gau												
	DA	820	73	8.9	(3.8-19.6)	960	39	4.1	(0.8-18.1)	5.8	(2.3-9.3)	1	(ref)
	IDA1	579	29	5.0	(1.8-12.9)	574	11	1.9	(0.8-4.5)	2.8	(-0.7-6.3)	0.8	(0.4-1.9)
	IDA2	698	26	3.7	(1.6-8.6)	713	15	2.1	(1.0-4.2)	2.2	(-0.0-4.4)	0.7	(0.3-1.8)

DA: diethylcarbamazine and albendazole; IDA: ivermectin, diethylcarbamazine and albendazole; CFA: circulating filarial antigen; Mf: microfilariae; CI: confidence intervals; Ref: reference group; +: positive
^a Mf denominator Baseline N=3637 excludes n=71 declined, n=93 ineligible, n=11 unreadable; 12months N=3770 excludes n=15 declined, n=112 ineligible, n=1 unreadable; participants are grouped into the village randomisation they were resident at time of testing

^b CFA denominator Baseline N=3659 excludes n=60 declined, n=93 ineligible; 12 months N=3773 excludes n=13 declined, n=112 ineligible; participants are grouped into the village randomisation they were resident at time of testing

^c Adjusted for clustering on village and stratified by island

^d Adjusted for clustering on village

^e Adjusted for clustering by village, stratified by island and baseline Mf prevalence

Supplementary Table 8. Village baseline and 12-month microfilariae prevalence

Village ^a	Microfilariae positive								Absolute reduction ^f
	Prevalence at baseline				Prevalence at 12 months				
	N ^b	n	%	(95% CI)	N ^c	n	%	(95% CI)	
DA									
2	18	0	0·0	(0-18·5) ^c	11	0	0·0	(0-28·5) ^c	-
3	161	5	3·1	(1·0-7·1)	156	4	2·6	(0·7-6·4)	0·5
4	83	16	19·3	(11·4-29·4)	79	11	13·9	(7·2-23·5)	5·4
8	74	3	4·1	(0·8-11·4)	80	1	1·3	(0·0-6·8)	2·8
16	82	1	1·2	(0·0-6·6)	86	1	1·2	(0·0-6·3)	0·1
18	207	19	9·2	(5·6-14·0)	224	9	4·0	(1·9-7·5)	5·2
26	256	1	0·4	(0·0-2·2)	275	0	0·0	(0-1·3) ^c	0·4
29	166	1	0·6	(0·0-3·3)	254	0	0·0	(0-1·4) ^c	0·6
30	58	0	0·0	(0-6·2) ^c	52	0	0·0	(0-6·8) ^e	-
32	98	0	0·0	(0-3·7) ^c	120	0	0·0	(0-3·0) ^e	-
34	35	1	2·9	(0·1-14·9)	35	0	0·0	(0-10·0) ^e	2·9
Total DA ^d	1238	47	3·8	(1·5-9·1)	1372	26	1·9	(0·7-5·2)	1·6
IDA1									
6	66	6	9·1	(3·4-18·7)	63	5	7·9	(2·6-17·6)	1·2
7	44	3	6·8	(1·4-18·7)	49	4	8·2	(2·3-19·6)	-1·3
10	193	7	3·6	(1·5-7·3)	230	0	0·0	(0-1·6) ^d	3·6
13	50	2	4·0	(0·5-13·7)	50	5	10·0	(3·3-21·8)	-6·0
15	121	6	5·0	(1·8-10·5)	107	1	0·9	(0·0-5·1)	4·0
17	74	12	16·2	(8·7-26·6)	83	6	7·2	(2·7-15·1)	9·0
19	81	0	0·0	(0-4·5) ^c	73	0	0·0	(0-4·9) ^c	-
22	111	4	3·6	(1·0-9·0)	114	0	0·0	(0-3·2) ^c	3·6
24	38	0	0·0	(0-9·3) ^c	36	0	0·0	(0-9·7) ^c	-
25	72	2	2·8	(0·3-9·7)	79	0	0·0	(0-4·6) ^c	2·8
27	117	1	0·9	(0·0-4·7)	119	0	0·0	(0-3·1) ^c	0·9
35	159	1	0·6	(0·0-3·5)	153	0	0·0	(0-2·4) ^c	0·6
Total IDA1 ^d	1126	44	3·9	(2·2-6·6)	1156	21	1·8	(0·7-4·6)	1·5
IDA2									
1	87	2	2·3	(0·3-8·1)	128	0	0·0	(0-2·8) ^e	2·3
5	173	11	6·4	(3·2-11·1)	141	4	2·8	(0·8-7·1)	3·5
9	48	7	14·6	(6·1-27·8)	30	5	16·7	(5·6-34·7)	-2·1
11	132	18	13·6	(8·2-20·7)	107	12	11·2	(5·9-18·8)	2·4
12	104	7	6·7	(2·7-13·4)	94	3	3·2	(0·7-9·0)	3·5
14	31	0	0·0	(0-11·2) ^c	29	0	0·0	(0-11·9) ^c	-
20	86	0	0·0	(0-4·2) ^c	107	1	0·9	(0·0-5·1)	-0·9
21	73	1	1·4	(0·0-7·4)	94	0	0·0	(0-3·8) ^c	1·4
23	119	3	2·5	(0·5-7·2)	106	0	0·0	(0-3·4) ^c	2·5
28	139	0	0·0	(0-2·6) ^c	125	0	0·0	(0-2·9) ^c	-
31	170	0	0·0	(0-2·1) ^c	189	0	0·0	(0-1·9) ^c	-
33	111	0	0·0	(0-3·3) ^c	92	0	0·0	(0-3·9) ^c	-
Total IDA2 ^d	1273	49	3·8	(1·9-7·7)	1242	25	2·0	(0·7-5·3)	1·1
Total all ^d	3637	140	3·8	(2·6-5·6)	3770	72	1·9	(1·1-3·2)	1·4

DA: diethylcarbamazine and albendazole; IDA1: ivermectin one dose, diethylcarbamazine and albendazole; IDA2: ivermectin two dose with DA; CI: confidence intervals

^a Villages 1-17 are on Rotuma; Villages 18-35 are on Gau; participants are grouped into the village they were resident at time of testing

^b Denominator Baseline (N=3637) excludes n=71 declined, n=93 ineligible, n=11 unreadable

^c Denominator 12 months (N=3770) excludes n=15 declined, n=112 ineligible, n=1 unreadable

^d Prevalence treatment group totals adjusted for clustering on village and stratified by island, absolute reduction adjusted for clustering on village

^e Confidence interval is one-sided, 97·5%

^f See Supplementary Table 7 for absolute reduction 95% confidence intervals for each treatment total
The intracluster correlation coefficient for Mf at baseline was 0·205 and 12 months was 0·411.

Supplementary Table 9. Village baseline and 12-month circulating filarial antigen prevalence

Village ^a	Circulating filarial antigen positive								
	Prevalence at baseline				Prevalence at 12 months				Absolute reduction ^f
	N ^b	n	%	(95% CI)	N ^c	n	%	(95% CI)	%
DA									
2	18	7	38.9	(17.3-64.3)	11	4	36.4	(10.9-69.2)	2.5
3	161	37	23.0	(16.7-30.3)	156	20	12.8	(8.0-19.1)	10.2
4	83	40	48.2	(37.1-59.4)	79	33	41.8	(30.8-53.4)	6.4
8	74	17	23.0	(14.0-34.2)	80	8	10.0	(4.4-18.8)	13.0
16	83	12	14.5	(7.7-23.9)	86	5	5.8	(1.9-13.0)	8.6
18	207	41	19.8	(14.6-25.9)	224	34	15.2	(10.7-20.6)	4.6
26	256	11	4.3	(2.2-7.6)	275	3	1.1	(0.2-3.2)	3.2
29	166	4	2.4	(0.7-6.1)	254	0	0.0	(0-1.4) ^e	2.4
30	58	9	15.5	(7.3-27.4)	52	1	1.9	(0.0-10.3)	13.6
32	98	6	6.1	(2.3-12.9)	120	1	0.8	(0.0-4.6)	5.3
34	35	2	5.7	(0.7-19.2)	35	0	0.0	(0-10.0) ^e	5.7
Total DA ^d	1239	186	15.0	(8.8-24.4)	1372	109	7.9	(3.5-17.1)	6.9
IDA1									
6	67	19	28.4	(18.0-40.7)	63	11	17.5	(9.1-29.1)	10.9
7	47	13	27.7	(15.6-42.6)	50	13	26.0	(14.6-40.3)	1.7
10	194	35	18.0	(12.9-24.2)	230	24	10.4	(6.8-15.1)	7.6
13	59	14	23.7	(13.6-36.6)	50	14	28.0	(16.2-42.5)	-4.3
15	121	17	14.0	(8.4-21.5)	107	13	12.1	(6.6-19.9)	1.9
17	75	18	24.0	(14.9-35.3)	83	13	15.7	(8.6-25.3)	8.3
19	81	1	1.2	(0.0-6.7)	73	0	0.0	(0.4-9) ^e	1.2
22	112	17	15.2	(9.1-23.2)	114	5	4.4	(1.4-9.9)	10.8
24	38	1	2.6	(0.1-13.8)	36	1	2.8	(0.1-14.5)	-0.1
25	72	4	5.6	(1.5-13.6)	79	2	2.5	(0.3-8.8)	3.0
27	117	3	2.6	(0.5-7.3)	119	3	2.5	(0.5-7.2)	0.0
35	159	3	1.9	(0.4-5.4)	153	0	0.0	(0.2-4) ^e	1.9
Total IDA1 ^d	1142	145	12.7	(8.5-18.5)	1157	99	8.6	(5.5-13.0)	3.6
IDA2									
1	87	18	20.7	(12.7-30.7)	128	10	7.8	(3.8-13.9)	12.9
5	174	41	23.6	(17.5-30.6)	141	23	16.3	(10.6-23.5)	7.3
9	48	17	35.4	(22.2-50.5)	30	7	23.3	(9.9-42.3)	12.1
11	136	54	39.7	(31.4-48.4)	109	38	34.9	(26.0-44.6)	4.8
12	104	23	22.1	(14.6-31.3)	94	17	18.1	(10.9-27.4)	4.0
14	31	6	19.4	(7.5-37.5)	29	2	6.9	(0.8-22.8)	12.5
20	86	3	3.5	(0.7-9.9)	107	3	2.8	(0.6-8.0)	0.7
21	73	8	11.0	(4.9-20.5)	94	5	5.3	(1.7-12.0)	5.6
23	119	10	8.4	(4.1-14.9)	106	4	3.8	(1.0-9.3)	4.6
28	139	1	0.7	(0.0-3.9)	125	1	0.8	(0.0-4.4)	-0.1
31	170	1	0.6	(0.0-3.2)	189	2	1.1	(0.1-3.8)	-0.5
33	111	3	2.7	(0.6-7.7)	92	0	0.0	(0.3-9) ^e	2.7
Total IDA2 ^d	1278	185	14.5	(8.3-24.0)	1244	112	9.0	(4.6-16.8)	5.6
Total all ^d	3659	516	14.1	(11.3-17.5)	3773	320	8.5	(6.2-11.5)	5.3

DA: diethylcarbamazine and albendazole; IDA1: ivermectin one dose, diethylcarbamazine and albendazole; IDA2: ivermectin two dose with DA; CI: confidence intervals

^a Villages 1-17 are on Rotuma; Villages 18-35 are on Gau; participants are grouped into the village they were resident at time of testing

^b Denominator Baseline (N=3659) excludes n=60 declined, n=93 ineligible

^c Denominator 12 months (N=3773) excludes n=13 declined, n=112 ineligible

^d Prevalence treatment group totals adjusted for clustering on village and stratified by island, absolute reduction adjusted for clustering on village

^e Confidence interval is one-sided, 97.5%

^f See Supplementary Table 7 for absolute reduction 95% confidence intervals for each treatment total
The intracluster correlation coefficient for CFA at baseline was 0.102 and 12 months was 0.167.

Supplementary Table 10. Treatment received by participants enrolled at 24-month follow-up

Treatment baseline	Treatment 12 months	N	%
DA	IDA1	20	21·7
IDA1	IDA1	27	29·3
IDA2	IDA1	28	30·4
DA	No treatment	1	1·1
IDA1	No treatment	1	1·1
IDA2	No treatment ^a	8	8·7
No treatment	IDA1	7	7·6
Total		92	100

DA: diethylcarbamazine and albendazole; IDA1: ivermectin one dose, diethylcarbamazine and albendazole; IDA2: ivermectin two dose with DA

^a n=1 enrolled and tested but ineligible for treatment

Supplementary Table 11. Individual efficacy of Mf clearance at 12 and 24 months among the 66 participants who were tested and treated at all three timepoints (baseline, 12 months, 24 months)

Treatment	Mf clearance 12 months			Mf clearance 24 months		
	N	n	%	N	n	%
DA & IDA1	15	9	60·0	15	12	80·0
IDA1 & IDA1	24	16	66·7	24	14	58·3
IDA2 & IDA1	27	17	63·0	27	13	48·1
Total	66	42	63·6	66	39	59·1

DA: diethylcarbamazine and albendazole; IDA1: ivermectin one dose, diethylcarbamazine and albendazole; IDA2: ivermectin two dose with DA

Supplementary Table 12. Clearance of Mf at 24 months by treatment group among the 24 participants who were positive for Mf at both baseline and 12 months, and whom received treatment at baseline and 12 months

Treatment	Mf clearance 24 months		
	N	n	%
DA & IDA1	6	3	50
IDA1 & IDA1	8	3	37.5
IDA2 & IDA1	10	0	0
Total	24	6	25

DA: diethylcarbamazine and albendazole; IDA1: ivermectin one dose, diethylcarbamazine and albendazole; IDA2: ivermectin two dose with DA

Supplementary Table 13. Geometric mean microfilarial density (Mf/ml) at the three timepoints in those positive for Mf at baseline and 24 months

Treatment	Baseline			12 months			24 months		
	N	Gmean Mf density Mf/ml	Range Mf/ml	N	Gmean Mf density Mf/ml	Range Mf/ml	N	Gmean Mf density Mf/ml	Range Mf/ml
DA & IDA	3	442	67-1754	3	178	100-484	3	48	33-67
IDA 2 rounds	24	325	17-9168	15	121	17-952	24	63	17-1703

DA: diethylcarbamazine and albendazole; IDA: ivermectin, diethylcarbamazine and albendazole; Gmean: geometric mean; Mf: microfilariae; Mf/ml: microfilariae per millilitre of blood

Supplementary Table 14. Clearance of microfilariae at 24 months in 10 individuals who were microfilariae positive and received treatment at baseline only

Treatment	Mf clearance 24 months		
	N	n	%
1 round DA	1	0	0
1 round IDA1	1	0	0
1 round IDA2	8	2	25
Total	10	2	20

DA: diethylcarbamazine and albendazole; IDA1: ivermectin one dose, diethylcarbamazine and albendazole; IDA2: ivermectin two dose with DA; Mf: microfilariae

Supplementary Figure 1. Randomisation, treatment, adverse event monitoring, and follow-up flowchart

DA: diethylcarbamazine and albendazole; IDA1: ivermectin one dose, diethylcarbamazine and albendazole; IDA2: ivermectin two dose with DA; AE: adverse event; D: day

^a Permethrin given to participants with scabies and their household contacts on day 8.

^b Permethrin given to participants excluded from ivermectin as alternative for scabies MDA on day 0.

^c Permethrin given to participants excluded from ivermectin as alternative for scabies MDA on day 0 and day 8.

^d Permethrin given to participants with scabies and their household contacts.

Supplementary Figure 2. Details of number of participants that completed filariasis testing for circulating filarial antigen and microfilariae at baseline and 12 months

DA: diethylcarbamazine and albendazole; IDA1: ivermectin one dose, diethylcarbamazine and albendazole; IDA2: ivermectin two doses, diethylcarbamazine and albendazole; LF: lymphatic filariasis; CFA: circulating filarial antigen; Mf: microfilariae

^a n=1 not treated at baseline, n=1 originally from IDA2 village.

Supplementary Figure 3. Microfilarial density change over time grouped by treatment and sex

DA: diethylcarbamazine and albendazole; IDA: ivermectin, diethylcarbamazine and albendazole; 12m: 12-month follow-up; Microfilarial count: a log of the estimate microfilariae density in one millilitre of blood

^a Male N=90 (DA n=32, IDA n=58)

^b Female N=21 (DA n=7, IDA n=14)

Supplementary Figure 4. Microfilarial density change over time grouped by treatment and island

DA: diethylcarbamazine and albendazole; IDA: ivermectin, diethylcarbamazine and albendazole; 12m: 12-month follow-up; Microfilarial count: a log of the estimate microfilariae density in one millilitre of blood;

^a Rotuma N=84 (DA n=20, IDA n=64)

^b Gau N=27 (DA n=19, IDA n=8)

Supplementary Figure 5. Eligibility and enrolment for 24-month follow-up

Mf: microfilariae

Supplementary Figure 6. Microfilarial smear and circulating filarial antigen test results and treatment received by the 92 participants followed up at 24 months

DA: diethylcarbamazine and albendazole; IDA1: ivermectin one dose, diethylcarbamazine and albendazole; IDA2: ivermectin two dose with DA; 12m: 12-month follow-up; 24m: 24-month follow-up

Supplementary Figure 7. Individual efficacy of treatments on microfilarial density at 12 months and 24 months among the 66 participants who were tested and treated at all three timepoints (baseline, 12 months and 24 months)

DA: diethylcarbamazine and albendazole, N=15; IDA1: ivermectin one dose, diethylcarbamazine and albendazole, N=24; IDA2: ivermectin two dose with DA, N=27; Microfilarial density: a log of the estimate microfilariae density in one millilitre of blood

Supplementary Figure 8. Baseline and 12-month age-specific prevalence of filariasis infection with 95% confidence intervals shaded for males (left) and females (right) measured by microfilariae (top) and circulating filarial antigen (bottom)

Mf: microfilarial; CFA: circulating filarial antigen

Supplementary Protocol. Community Based Safety of 2-drug (Diethylcarbamazine and Albendazole) versus 3-drug (Ivermectin, Diethylcarbamazine and Albendazole) Therapy for Lymphatic Filariasis in Fiji – Protocol v6.0 6th August 2019

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